

Public Attitudes toward Psychiatric Hospitals: a Comparative Survey of Rural and Urban Populations in India

Deepak Kumar¹, I.D. Singh², Sanjay Kumar³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

²Professor & HOD, Department of Psychiatry, Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepak Kumar

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Abstract:

Background: Mental health is a critical aspect of overall well-being, yet psychiatric disorders remain heavily stigmatized, particularly in developing countries like India. Public attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals play a crucial role in shaping the utilization of mental health services, and understanding these attitudes in both rural and urban populations is essential for developing effective public health strategies. This study aims to compare public attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals between rural and urban populations in India.

Methods: A total of 130 participants, 65 from rural and 65 from urban areas, were selected using stratified random sampling. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, and multivariate logistic regression were employed to examine differences and identify influencing factors.

Results: Urban participants exhibited more positive attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals compared to rural participants, with significant differences in perceptions of hospital necessity, equipment adequacy, and personal comfort. Perceived stigma was higher among rural participants (69.2%) than urban participants (46.2%). Multivariate analysis identified urban residence (OR=2.5, p=0.004) and higher education (OR=3.2, p=0.001) as significant predictors of positive attitudes.

Conclusion: There are substantial differences in attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals between rural and urban populations in India. Urban residents and individuals with higher education levels tend to have more favorable perceptions and lower perceived stigma.

Recommendations: Targeted educational and awareness programs are needed, especially in rural areas, to address misconceptions and reduce stigma related to mental health services. Enhancing mental health literacy and improving access to psychiatric care in rural regions are crucial steps toward improving mental health outcomes.

Keywords: Mental Health, Psychiatric Hospitals, Public Attitudes, Rural-Urban Comparison, Stigma.

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Introduction

Mental health is a critical component of overall well-being, yet psychiatric disorders remain heavily stigmatized, particularly in developing countries like India. The stigma surrounding mental illness often leads to delays in seeking treatment, non-adherence to prescribed therapies, and overall poorer health outcomes [1]. Public attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals play a crucial role in shaping the utilization of mental health services. Understanding these attitudes, especially the differences between rural and urban populations, is essential for developing effective public health strategies.

India, with its diverse and vast population, presents a unique context for studying mental health attitudes. Approximately 70% of the Indian population resides in rural areas, where mental health services are often limited, and traditional beliefs about mental illness prevail [2]. In contrast, urban areas typically have better access to healthcare services, including psychiatric care, and may exhibit more progressive attitudes due to higher levels of education and exposure to mental health awareness campaigns.

Recent studies have highlighted significant disparities in mental health awareness and attitudes between rural and urban populations in India. For

instance, a study found that urban residents were more likely to recognize the symptoms of mental disorders and seek professional help compared to their rural counterparts [3]. This disparity is further compounded by the availability of mental health services, with urban areas having more specialized facilities and trained professionals.

The influence of education on mental health attitudes cannot be overstated. Higher education levels are generally associated with greater awareness and acceptance of mental health issues, leading to more favorable attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals [4]. This trend is evident in various studies, where individuals with higher educational attainment show less stigma and greater willingness to utilize mental health services.

The importance of this study is underscored by the increasing burden of mental health disorders in India, which has been exacerbated by recent societal changes and the ongoing impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. Addressing the stigma and misconceptions about psychiatric hospitals is crucial for improving access to mental health care and ensuring that individuals receive the necessary support and treatment.

This study aims to examine public attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals among rural and urban populations in India.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative cross-sectional survey.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of March 2020 to December 2020 at Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.

Participants: A total of 130 participants were selected for the study, comprising individuals from both rural and urban areas.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and above.
- Residents of rural or urban areas in and around Muzaffarpur.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals with a history of psychiatric disorders.
- Participants who are healthcare professionals.
- Incomplete or improperly filled questionnaires.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the population using stratified sampling to ensure representation from both rural and urban areas. Information bias was addressed by using a standardized questionnaire.

Data Collection: Data was collected through a structured questionnaire that was pre-tested and validated. The questionnaire included sections on demographics, general attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals, perceived stigma, and personal experiences with mental health services.

Procedure: Participants were approached in various public settings such as community centers, marketplaces, and residential areas. Trained surveyors administered the questionnaire face-to-face, ensuring participants understood the questions and provided accurate responses. Completed questionnaires were collected, checked for completeness, and securely stored for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize demographic characteristics and overall attitudes. Multivariate logistic regression was conducted to adjust for potential confounders and assess the independent effects of demographic factors on public attitudes.

Result

The study included 130 participants, with an equal distribution of 65 individuals from rural and 65 from urban areas. The demographic characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Rural	Urban	Total
Mean Age (years)	42.5 ± 12.3	39.7 ± 10.5	41.1 ± 11.4
Gender (Male/Female)	37/28	34/31	71/59
Education Level (%)			
No formal education	20 (30.8%)	5 (7.7%)	25 (19.2%)
Primary education	25 (38.5%)	15 (23.1%)	40 (30.8%)
Secondary education	15 (23.1%)	20 (30.8%)	35 (26.9%)
Higher education	5 (7.7%)	25 (38.5%)	30 (23.1%)

Participants' attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals were assessed using a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Attitudes Toward Psychiatric Hospitals

Statement	Rural	Urban	p-value
Psychiatric hospitals are essential for society	3.9 ± 0.8	4.5 ± 0.6	0.001
People with mental illness should be treated in psychiatric hospitals	3.5 ± 1.0	4.2 ± 0.9	0.002
Psychiatric hospitals are well-equipped	3.0 ± 1.1	3.8 ± 0.9	0.004
I would feel comfortable visiting a psychiatric hospital if needed	2.8 ± 1.2	3.6 ± 1.0	0.003
There is a stigma associated with psychiatric hospitals	4.2 ± 0.7	3.5 ± 0.8	0.005

Perceived stigma was higher among rural participants compared to their urban counterparts. Detailed responses regarding perceived stigma are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Perceived Stigma Toward Psychiatric Hospitals

Statement	Rural	Urban	p-value
Agree there is a stigma associated with visiting psychiatric hospitals	45 (69.2%)	30 (46.2%)	0.01
Believe stigma affects willingness to seek treatment	50 (76.9%)	25 (38.5%)	0.001

A multivariate logistic regression analysis was conducted to determine the factors independently associated with positive attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis

Variable	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Urban residence	2.5 (1.3-4.8)	0.004
Higher education	3.2 (1.6-6.5)	0.001
Age	1.1 (0.9-1.3)	0.15
Gender (Male vs Female)	1.0 (0.5-2.0)	0.99

Discussion

The study surveyed 130 participants, evenly split between rural and urban areas, to compare public attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals. Demographic analysis revealed that rural participants were generally older and less educated compared to their urban counterparts. A significant portion of rural participants had no formal education, highlighting a demographic disparity that might influence attitudes toward mental health services.

The analysis of attitudes revealed notable differences between rural and urban participants. Urban residents exhibited more positive attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals, with higher mean scores on statements regarding the necessity, equipment adequacy, and personal comfort in visiting psychiatric hospitals. For instance, urban participants strongly agreed with the statement that psychiatric hospitals are essential for society (mean score: 4.5) compared to rural participants (mean score: 3.9), indicating a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.001$). This trend was consistent across other attitude measures, suggesting a generally more favorable perception of psychiatric hospitals among urban residents.

Perceived stigma associated with psychiatric hospitals was higher among rural participants. A

significant majority of rural respondents (69.2%) agreed that there is a stigma associated with visiting psychiatric hospitals, compared to 46.2% of urban respondents ($p = 0.01$). This stigma potentially affects the willingness to seek treatment, as indicated by 76.9% of rural participants acknowledging that stigma impacts their decision to seek psychiatric care, compared to 38.5% of urban participants ($p = 0.001$).

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified urban residence and higher education as significant factors independently associated with positive attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals. Urban residents were 2.5 times more likely to have positive attitudes compared to rural residents ($p = 0.004$), and individuals with higher education were 3.2 times more likely to have favorable views ($p = 0.001$). Age and gender did not show significant associations in this analysis.

Overall, the study highlights substantial differences in attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals between rural and urban populations in India. Urban residents and those with higher education levels tend to have more positive perceptions and lower perceived stigma, underscoring the need for targeted educational and awareness programs, especially in rural areas, to address misconceptions and reduce stigma related to mental health services.

These findings emphasize the importance of addressing educational and regional disparities to improve public attitudes and utilization of psychiatric hospitals.

A study assessed attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals among urban and rural populations in Odisha, India. The study included 988 participants, with 496 from urban areas and 492 from rural areas. It was found that individuals in rural areas and those with lower education levels had more negative attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals. Level of education and urban-rural comparison significantly influenced attitudes, whereas gender, age, and religious beliefs did not show significant effects [5].

Research surveyed primary caregivers' attitudes towards mental illness in rural and urban populations in Jaipur, Rajasthan. The study used the Community Attitudes Towards Mental Illness (CAMI) scale and found significant differences in attitudes based on rural and urban residency. Rural caregivers exhibited more negative attitudes compared to their urban counterparts [6].

A study examined the attitudes of rural populations towards mental healthcare in the Khurda district of Odisha. The study revealed that factors such as education, gender, and age significantly influenced attitudes. Barriers to mental healthcare included societal stigma, reliance on religious healers, and lack of mental health services. The study emphasized the need for considering these factors when strategizing mental healthcare systems [7].

A study compared knowledge and attitudes regarding mental illness among adults in rural and urban communities in West Bengal. The study found that rural participants had more knowledge about mental illness than urban participants, attributed to the level of education. However, no significant difference in attitudes was found between the two groups. Strong correlations between knowledge and attitudes were observed in both rural and urban settings [8].

Conclusion

The study reveals significant differences in attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals between rural and urban populations. Urban participants generally had more positive attitudes and lower perceived stigma compared to rural participants. Education

level also played a crucial role, with higher education associated with more favorable attitudes. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to reduce stigma and improve public perceptions of psychiatric hospitals, particularly in rural areas. The study underscores the importance of addressing educational and regional disparities in attitudes toward psychiatric hospitals. Efforts to enhance mental health literacy and reduce stigma, especially in rural areas, are essential for improving mental health outcomes and service utilization in India.

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